

Advanced Fuels and Powertrains

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Introduction, Background

- ▶ The transition towards net-zero emissions has driven significant advancements in internal combustion engine (ICE) technology, with a strong focus on efficiency and emissions reduction [1]. This study involves modelling a **single-cylinder gasoline direct injection (GDI) engine** in **AVL CRUISE M**, simulating **Spark Ignition (SI)** and **Homogeneous Charge Compression Ignition (HCCI)** combustion modes [1]. By analysing engine performance, calibration, and optimization strategies, the goal is to explore modifications that enhance efficiency while minimizing emissions [1].

References:

[1] Canvas, Advanced Fuels and Powertrain Systems 2024/25)

Compression Ignition

Spark Ignition

Fig. 1 Compression Ignition and Spark Ignition cylinder [1]

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Introduction, Background

- ▶ This project follows a structured approach, beginning with the setup of the engine model using predefined **geometry, intake/exhaust layouts, and combustion parameters** [1]. The model will be calibrated using experimental in-cylinder pressure data, followed by an evaluation of modifications such as **valve timing adjustments, alternative fuels, and exhaust aftertreatment technologies** [1]. Additionally, the potential for integrating zero-carbon fuels and hybridization strategies will be explored within the broader context of sustainable transportation [1].

Compression Ignition

Spark Ignition

References:

[1] Canvas, Advanced Fuels and Powertrain Systems 2024/25)

Fig. 1 Compression Ignition and Spark Ignition cylinder [1]

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- ▶ **Aim:** To simulate experimental data through AVL Cruise M so as to evaluate engine performance of HCCI and SI combustion models
- ▶ **Objectives:**
 - ▶ 1. Calibrate engine performance parameters with experimental results: IMEP, max pressure, pressure trace and exhaust emissions.
 - ▶ 2. Model evaluation
 - ▶ 3. Evaluate and discussion of modifications on the incorporation of an aftertreatment system and their function in hybrid vehicles.

Model (SI)

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- ▶ Throttle
- ▶ Spark Ignition
- ▶ Excess air ratio (λ) is 1
- ▶ Air fuel ratio 14.7

p-V graphs (SI)

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Model (HCCI)

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p-V graphs (HCCI)

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Results – Settings

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		Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7
Compression ratio	-	11.5	11.5	11.5	11.5	11.5	11.5	11.5
Air fuel ratio	-	17.49	17.64	19.26	14.7	14.7	14.7	14.7
Excess air ratio (lambda)		1.19	1.2	1.31	1	1	1	1
Throttle	degrees -	-	-	-	90	4.7	6.4	7.5
Combustion shift	degrees	9.8	10.3	6.5	2	12	10	11
Linear thermal model multiplier	-	1.25	4.1	1.05	0.4	1	1	1
Linear thermal model multiplier	-	3	1	1	0.5	1	1	1
Piston thermal model multiplier	-	3	1	1	0.5	1	1	1
Exhaust temperature	C	313.2	374.9	408.7	698.7	539.1	542.1	560.3

		Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7
IMEP (given)	bar	1.81	2.8	3.48	10.04	1.73	2.58	3.25
IMEP (obtained)	bar	1.81	2.8	3.5	10	1.71	2.58	3.23
Pmax (given)	bar	29.8	38.3	40.3	47.2	14.9	21.1	27.6
Pmax (obtained)	bar	29.8	38.3	40.5	47.8	14.8	21.6	26.8
Pmax CAD (given)	degree	371	369.5	372	382	372.5	371.5	369.5
Pmax CAD (obtained)	degree	378.8	377.7	377.3	383	376.4	375.6	375.3
CO2 (given)	%	11.73	11.61	10.46	13.55	13.49	13.51	13.67
CO2 (obtained)	%	20.72	20.54	20.73	19.1	20.75	20.45	20.13
CO (given)	%	0.19	0.072	0.0613	1.312	1.167	1.073	1.028
CO (obtained)	%	0.14	0.26	0.14	1.17	0.12	0.31	0.52
NO (given)	ppm	4	29	66	2733	994	1859	2656
NO (obtained)	ppm	407	751	423	3585	314	833	1389

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Results – Exhaust gases

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Modification – Fuel (Methane)

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		Case 1	Case 1 mod	Case 4	Case 4 mod	Case 5	Case 5 mod
Air fuel ratio	-	17.49	20.49	14.7	17.22	14.7	17.22
IMEP	bar	1.81	1.93	10	9.96	1.71	1.7
Pmax	bar	29.8	30.8	47.8	48.5	14.8	14.9
CO2 %(m/m)	%	20.72	14.92	19.1	14	20.75	14.96
CO	%	0.14	0.04	1.17	0.57	0.12	0.06
NO	ppm	407	234	3585	2768	314	210

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- ▶ **Unmodified:** Gasoline
- ▶ **Modified:** Methane

Modification – Fuel (Methane)

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Modification – Fuel (Methane)

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Modification – Combustion shift angle

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		Case 1	Case 1 mod	Case 4	Case 4 mod	Case 5	Case 5 mod
Combustion shift angle	degrees	9.8	3	2	0.6	12	3.6
Pmax CAD	degree	378.8	372.1	383	381.2	376.4	370.9
IMEP	bar	1.81	1.34	10	10.5	1.71	1.58
Pmax	bar	29.8	35.2	47.8	49.9	14.8	18.6
CO2 %(m/m)	%	20.72	20.77	19.1	19.12	20.75	20.72
CO	%	0.14	0.11	1.17	1.16	0.12	0.14
NO	ppm	407	312	3585	3572	314	372

Modification – Combustion shift angle

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Combustion shift angle

Pmax CAD

IMEP

Pmax

Modification – Combustion shift angle

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- ▶ Due to high efficiency depicted by the compression ignition, low emission and valve delay we compare the spark ignitions rate of heat transfer using logarithmic presentation and slope generated in the plot.
- ▶ The CO values for case 5, 6, 7 are not coherent as the thermal model was not changed so as to maintain the IMEP and max pressures already obtained.
- ▶ The anomaly seen in all cases is caused by the mistaken input of grams instead of molar mass – this was adjusted.
- ▶ The differences between HCCI and SI combustion methods were evident in the disparity in CO₂, CO and NO, yet following the same trend in IMEP and exhaust gases obtained.

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- ▶ Through the use of AVL the simulation managed to achieve within 1% accuracy IMEP and peak pressure values for SI and HCCI configurations.
- ▶ Reduction of emissions by 27-28% was achieved by modifying the gas composition and injection options from gasoline to methane.
- ▶ Modifications reduced the shift angles by a ratio of 3.3. The IMEP decreases 26% for case 1, 5% increases for case 4, 7% decreases for case 5. 18% Peak pressure increase for case 1, 4% increase for case 4 and 26% increase for case 5. Emission product changes were negligible.
- ▶ Overall the simulation successfully validated the model, with the model modifications revealing the large decrease in combustion products produced by changing the fuel. Proving the possibility in reducing emissions through the use of alternative fuels without reducing performance.

Q & A

Any questions?